

ETHICS OF THE SCIENCE OF MYSTICISM IN YOUTH EDUCATION

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Annotation. This article reflects the processes associated with the upbringing of a perfect person in the doctrine of mysticism, which is of great importance in the upbringing of the younger generation.

Keywords. Mysticism, philosophy, manifestation of mysticism, spirit, human perfection, equality, purity, perfection, hypocrisy

THE SUBJECT.

The invaluable cultural heritage, national-spiritual values accumulated over many years of history have a direct impact on the formation and development of our national culture and the ideology of national independence.

Knowledge, which has a great place in the upbringing of the younger generation, is valuable in its status. One such doctrine is mysticism-one of the very high-status Sciences about human perfection, moral purification.

In the science of mysticism, human perfection has been one of the central issues. Among them is grief for a person, contemplation of his spiritual perfection.

One of the most pressing questions of the field of philosophy is the fact that a person lives in the universe and its causes, ending in a special divine approach in mysticism. For example, the interior world, internal conflicts, the struggle between the soul and the body fall into the embodiment of these.

Mysticism scholars argue that the idea of confrontation with human zinc, that is, the existence of Merciful and satanic powers, with the support of God, it is desirable to strive for merciful qualities, defeating the Satanic vasavasa.

OBJECTIVES OF THE ARTICLE. The place of man in life, the way of life of society are also considered from this position; for example, Sufism seeks the root cause of social conflicts, wars and property inequality in human nature and behavior, explaining that the correction of human morality must begin with the destruction of negative, animal qualities in man.

Manifestations of Sufism had a negative reaction to the evil vices of human nature, called "nafs" or "nafsi ammar". People's attachment to worldly pleasures (accumulation of worldly goods, following the needs of the soul, greed) manifests itself in a critical situation, and it was argued that only the ability to keep oneself in balance, contentment and honesty will save humanity from the destruction to which it is subjected due to these vices.

Sufism focuses on the problem of the soul. It is claimed that man attains divinity by having free will.

These ideas are clearly expressed in the definitions given by the great sheikhs to the concept of "mysticism". Sheikh Nuri answered the question and said, "Sufism is the renunciation of spiritual pleasures." Or the answer of Sheikh Safi Alishah is: "Sufism crosses the paths of the soul." The words of Sheikh Ravim: "Sufism is self-sacrifice for God".

In Sufism, the following ideas are put forward about the soul. Nafs is a human philosophy that leads to selfishness, a person trapped in it does not distinguish between good and bad, does not care about what is bad, and prefers to benefit from the work of others rather than his own. A man afflicted with the ulcer of lust will follow the path of cruelty, cruelty and hypocrisy.

Therefore, there is much to be said about the abstinence, contentment, patience and poverty that Sufism demands. "You come into the world once, take what you get" is a well-known philosophy. The Communists are changing this to: "I'm a human being, so everything depends on me," but the goal is the same: to find a way out, to live well, to have nothing to do with others. The philosophy of

"everything is fair" deprives a person of faith, gives a fatwa to robbery and robbery, strengthens the instinct of barbarism.

A perfect person is an ideal, possessing all worldly and divine knowledge, whose soul is connected with the Absolute Spirit, full of goodness, whose image is beautiful, whose heart is full of kind feelings. The conscious state belongs to the old man, his eyes are lowered. The ideal that the mystics worshipped, the Perfect Man, was actually the ideal of the people, the ideal of literature.

Ibn Arabi said of Sufism: "Sufism is the attainment of the light of divine qualities by abstaining from bad morality." Sheikh Hariri expressed a similar opinion: "Sufism is the entry into good and high behavior and the exit from low behavior." Muhammad Ali bin Kassab "Sufi morality consists of Karima"

Based on these thoughts, we can be sure that Sufism provides a condition for having a divine status in exchange for morality in human qualities.

It is not for nothing that mature representatives of the world of Sufism emphasize this teaching as "the school of being free, to be free."

Sufism was described by scientists as knowledge that subordinates it and saves a person from egocentrism and selfishness.

In many studies, Sufism is defined as a "science". Najmiddin Kamilov described Sufism as "the science of unity", "the science of monotheism", and M.A. Joshon described it as "the science of soul training", "the science of internal jurisprudence", "the science of the state of the soul". the soul". He says that Sufism is the science of self—education, the science of knowing and knowing God (ma'rifatullah) and objective service in accordance with His will, and says that it is "the most honorable of sciences and the essence, essence and truth of Islam".

CONCLUSIONS. Sufism is a product of human thought, its ideological system is concepts such as equality, purity, and the pursuit of perfection. Although Sufism is a sect of Islam, it can unite the interests and goals of all nations, peoples, races and genders. Sufism is a religious and philosophical doctrine. Taking into

account the dangers of educating the younger generation in the context of the rapid growth of humanity today, this doctrine can be called one of the foundations of the idea of national independence.

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